

Revolutionizing the Textile Industry through Sustainable Green Technology

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Abstract:

Green technology refers to the development and use of environmentally friendly products and processes to reduce the negative impact of human activities on the environment. The textile industry is one of the largest and most polluting industries in the world, with a significant carbon footprint and a large amount of waste generated. Therefore, there is a growing need for the adoption of green technologies in the textile industry to reduce its impact on the environment. The adoption of green technologies in the textile industry can have a positive impact on various stages of the production process, including raw material production, yarn manufacturing, fabric production, dyeing and finishing, and waste management. Some examples of green technologies that can be used in the textile industry include organic and recycled fibres, low impact dyes, and water and energy-saving processes. The use of organic and recycled fibres can help reduce the environmental impact of textile production by reducing the use of pesticides and fertilizers in agriculture and reducing the amount of waste sent to landfills. Low impact dyes are also an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional dyes, as they require less water and energy and produce fewer harmful chemicals. In addition, water and energy-saving processes can help reduce the number of resources used in the production process, thereby reducing the carbon footprint of the textile industry. Overall, the adoption of green technologies in the textile industry can help reduce its negative impact on the environment and promote sustainable practices.

Keywords: Green technology, Eco-friendly process, Textile industries, Green textiles

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1. Introduction

Consumers are looking for healthier lifestyle options due to global pollution and rising awareness. Consumers today are more concerned about their health and actively promote greener lifestyles. Green or eco-friendly production involves practises like minimising and recycling. The non-toxic clean products and energy production strategies are the focus of the green system field. This technology can bring about innovation and change in daily life without harming the environment or compromising its sustainability. It is difficult to foresee how the technologies can be contained in this regard. There haven't been enough studies done in this field when the green textile and apparel sector is considered. Moore and Asley provided an illustration of how stakeholders working together might lead to greener production and boost productivity [1].

Fuzzy logic and the analytical hierarchy process were combined by Wang et al. to create a selection (decision-making) model for various green initiatives in the fashion industry [2]. Wu, et al. analysed Taiwan's textile and clothing producers and looked at the connections between organisational supports, social capital, and government involvement, green purchasing, consumer cooperation, eco-design, and investment recovery practises. This research focused on potential methods that could be used to enhance the general environment and working conditions in the textile sector. Furthermore, based on the green technology applications. The youthful, non-green textile sector can be changed to one that is more environmentally conscious and sustainable. According to the definition of a green environment, the analysis of the textile industry and lifecycle and the critical function of greening parameters are covered.

2. Materials & Methods

By enhancing the entire environmental and manipulation aspects of the textile industries with some focus on achieving an internationally recognised standard, the green technology in industrial textile can be improved. This article covered the textile industry's environmental benefits. The study of green technology focused on how much more environmentally friendly textile manufacture, use, and recycling would be. Additionally, by offering a major method to identify green businesses with low-cost measurement, this work aimed to ascertain the significances of green textiles industries in terms of both economic and environmental benefits. The textile industry has traditionally been associated with high levels of resource consumption, pollution, and waste. However, with the growing awareness of the environmental impacts of textile production, there has been a significant shift towards the use of green technologies and techniques that are more sustainable and eco-friendlier. By strengthening the whole environmental and manipulation aspects of the textile industries with some focus on obtaining an internationally recognised standard, the green technology in industrial textile can be improved. This article covered the textile industry's benefits for the environment. The study of green technology centred on how much more environmentally friendly textile production, use, and recycling would be. Additionally, by offering a major method to identify green businesses with low-cost measurement, this work aimed to ascertain the significances of green textiles industries in terms of both economic and environmental benefits [3]. Here are some examples:

2.1 Water-saving techniques

The textile industry is one of the largest consumers of water, with the dyeing and finishing processes alone using vast amounts of water. Green technologies like advanced dyeing processes, such as air dyeing and foam dyeing, and water recycling systems can help reduce the industry's water consumption. The textile industry is known for its high water consumption and environmental impact. However, there are several water-saving techniques that can be implemented in the textile industry using green technology. Here are some examples:

2.2 Recycling water

One effective technique is to recycle and reuse the wastewater generated during textile production. This can be done through various methods such as reverse osmosis, nanofiltration, or ultrafiltration. By reusing water, the amount of water used in the production process can be significantly reduced [4].

2.3 Eco-friendly dyes

Traditional textile dyes are known to be harmful to the environment due to their high chemical content. Eco-friendly dyes, on the other hand, are made from natural materials and are free from harmful chemicals. Recent research has revealed that some of these fibrous plants are rich suppliers of phytoestrogens as well as potentially effective natural medicines. More fashion and clothing companies are switching to eco-friendly textiles nowadays, with the justification being that no pollutant must be used throughout any stage of the textile's manufacture. Textiles may still reduce their environmental impact, whether in manufacture, distribution, or agriculture. The first phrase that may be used for the actual development of environmentally friendly textiles in this context is "green technology." The term "green technology" refers to a variety of procedures and goods that range from non-toxic cleaning agents to energy generation systems. Cleaning agents to energy generation systems [5].

Table 1: Estimated global tonnage of fibrous raw materials from agricultural crops

Crop	Plant component	Availability 000 tonnes
Cereals	Straw	
Barley	Straw	222.5
Oats	Straw	52.8
Rice	Straw	475.3
Rye	Straw	51.9
Wheat	Straw	749.7
Corn	Stalks	737.0
cotton	Mote	800
Bast Fibrous Plants	Straw	26
Seed grass	Straw	2
Oil Flax	Straw	3
Sorghum	Stalks	104.7
Sugarcane	Bagasse	100.2

2.4 Low water-use machinery

There are many types of machinery used in textile production, some of which use a lot of water. Low water-use machinery can be used instead, which reduces the amount of water needed for production. For example, some washing machines use less water by recycling the water within the machine.

2.5 Waterless processes

Some processes in textile production can be done without using any water at all. For example, some printing processes use heat transfer or digital printing instead of traditional screen printing, which requires water.

2.6 Rainwater harvesting

Textile companies can collect rainwater and use it for non-potable purposes such as cleaning, gardening, or cooling equipment. This reduces the demand for fresh water and lowers the company's overall water footprint. By implementing these and other green technologies, textile companies can significantly reduce their water consumption and environmental impact while still producing high-quality textiles [6].

2.7 Renewable energy sources

The textile industry is also a significant consumer of energy, primarily fossil fuels. The use of renewable energy sources like solar and wind power can help reduce the industry's carbon footprint and make textile production more sustainable. The textile industry is a significant consumer of energy and resources, and transitioning to renewable energy sources can help reduce its carbon footprint and contribute to sustainable development.

Figure 1: Eco friendly materials and their importance

2.8 Natural dyes

Natural dyes, on the other hand, are generally safe and pose fewer risks to human health. This makes textiles dyed with natural dyes a healthier and more appealing choice for consumers.

- **Consumer Demand for Sustainable Products:** In recent years, there has been a growing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly products, including textiles. Consumers are becoming more conscious of the environmental and social impacts of their purchasing decisions. By using natural dyes, textile manufacturers can cater to this demand and differentiate their products in the market.
- **Collaboration with Farmers and Artisans:** The shift towards natural dyes requires collaboration between textile manufacturers, farmers, and artisans. Farmers can cultivate dye-producing plants, ensuring a sustainable supply chain. Artisans skilled in natural dyeing techniques can contribute their expertise, promoting fair trade practices and supporting local economies.
- **Research and Development:** Further research and development in natural dye extraction, dyeing techniques, and colour fastness can improve the overall performance and durability of natural dyes. Innovations in this field can address some of the challenges associated with natural dyes, such as colour fading and limited shade range, making them more viable for large-scale textile production [7].

In summary, the use of natural dyes has the potential to transform the textile industry by promoting sustainability, preserving traditional knowledge, offering a diverse colour palette, enhancing consumer health and safety, meeting consumer demand for sustainable products, fostering collaborations, and driving research and development. By embracing natural dyes, we can create a more environmentally friendly and socially responsible textile industry.

2.8 Sustainable fibres

The use of sustainable fibres like organic cotton, hemp, bamboo, and recycled polyester can help reduce the environmental impact of textile production. These fibres are grown without the use of harmful chemicals and pesticides, and they require less water and energy to produce [8].

Fig:2 Types of Sustainable Fibres

2.10 Waste reduction and recycling

The textile industry generates a significant amount of waste, including scraps of fabric and unused material. The use of recycling techniques like closed-loop production and upcycling can help reduce waste and conserve resources. Waste reduction and recycling are important aspects of sustainable development, and the textile industry has a significant impact on the environment. Green technology offers innovative solutions for reducing waste and increasing recycling in the textile industry [9]. Here are some ways that green technology can be used to reduce waste and increase recycling in the textile industry:

- Use of Sustainable Materials:** Textile manufacturers can use sustainable materials such as organic cotton, hemp, bamboo, and recycled polyester to reduce the environmental impact of their products. These materials are grown without the use of harmful chemicals and can be recycled or biodegraded at the end of their life cycle.
- Water Conservation:** The textile industry is a water-intensive industry, and green technology can be used to reduce water consumption. Some techniques such as digital printing, dyeing, and finishing can help in reducing water usage up to 90%.
- Chemical Management:** The use of toxic chemicals in textile processing is a major environmental concern. Green technology can help textile manufacturers to use eco-friendly alternatives such as natural dyes, enzymes, and biodegradable chemicals.
- Recycling and Waste Reduction:** Green technology can help in the recycling of textile waste such as post-consumer waste and post-industrial waste. Textile waste can be repurposed for different purposes such as insulation, furniture padding, and carpet backing.
- Energy Efficiency:** The textile industry is energy-intensive, and green technology can be used to reduce energy consumption. Use of renewable energy such as solar and wind power can help in reducing the carbon footprint of the industry.

In conclusion, the textile industry can reduce waste and increase recycling by using green technology. The use of sustainable materials, water conservation, chemical management, recycling and waste reduction, and energy efficiency can help the industry to move towards a more sustainable future. Overall, the textile industry can significantly benefit from the use of green technologies and techniques. By reducing water and energy consumption, using sustainable fibres and natural dyes, and implementing waste reduction and recycling techniques, the industry can become more sustainable and environmentally friendly.

3. Results & Discussion

The possibilities to transform textiles were examined in this study, industry into the green textile sector has occurred in two stages created. It is anticipated that by comparing the price of making a garment in the nongreen textile

industry with the green textile industry, that green textiles have lower production costs. The price of clothes Because of the limited production, for green textile industries is less [10]. Green technology and circular economies are therefore the most important vital techniques for making textiles that are respectable, durable, and green of the surroundings.

3.1 Resent Progress on Greening Textile Industry

Making factories environmentally or eco-friendly is gaining importance internationally since the globe is becoming more susceptible for its inhabitant's day by day. Worldwide, unhealthful environments claim millions of lives each year. According to a new World Health Organisation report, environmental dangers now have a role in more than 100 of the most severe diseases and injuries in the world and account for 12.6 million fatalities year, or 23% of all deaths. In this case, green manufacturing is essential, and the idea should be encouraged. Interesting enough, a certification programme called Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) was created by organisations like the U.S. Green Building Council (USGBC) to assess a building's environmental performance and promote market adoption.

3.2 Economic advantages

If non-green industry is transformed into green industry, the following financial advantages will result.

- The working conditions and environment in factories are highly valued by well-known companies.
- Western consumers also favour purchasing goods made in environmentally conscious factories. Boost output and develop a brand image.
- Though establishing a green factory requires a 30 to 40% higher initial investment than a conventional one, it ultimately saves money by lowering the cost of utilities like power and water.
- Although adopting eco-friendly or green technology initially needs large investments, such a move may assist boost the country's competitiveness. For environmentally friendly items, buyers typically offer 10 to 15 percent more prices.

4. Conclusion

This study's goal was to assess the current state of raising awareness of the need for greener manufacturing in the textile industry. Industries must modify their current products due to the competitive climate. In the textile sector, there is a duty to practise environmental responsibility. The present green technology that might preserve the environment without having an impact on the textile industries was described in this paper. As a result, the most important variables in making textile and garment production more ecologically friendly are those that start with the product design stage, raw material selection, processing and production decisions, transportation, retailing, and waste management. Additionally, this article discussed current green technology research as well as available textile industry methods. Finally, it was determined that green technology in the textile industry can guarantee the environmental sustainability and friendliness.

5. Conflict of Interest

Author declares no conflict of interest.

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